

Research Article

Wudu' Wonder: Virtual Reality Ablution Education for Youth

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Abstract: Ablution is a ritual washing performed by Muslim and it is a part of compulsory activities to ensure cleanliness before the Muslim perform prayers. Knowledge on performing ablution procedures properly is a must as all Muslim have to pray. However, traditional methods of ablution education and lack of accessibility often struggles to engage youth learners due to uninteresting media usage. Wudu Wonder is a 3D educational virtual reality game designed to educate children on compulsory ablution procedures with motion capture technology from Kinect. The program aims to develop an educational interactive tool that tailors the youth learning experience by combining the engaging aspects of virtual reality education approach with ablution education. Utilizing ADDIE Model as the methodology for the foundation of this project serves the framework to develop an engaging educational tool. The User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) was implemented to evaluate the impact on user experience. The project achieves a high percentage of user satisfaction which is 85.2%. The research shows that Wudu Wonder is not only meets its educational goals but also provides an interesting and engaging medium for youth to learn ablution. Future research could offer all ablution procedures and multi-platform support. Wudu Wonder demonstrates the potential of VR technology in creating interactive learning experience.

Keywords: Ablution; education; virtual reality.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Ablution (Wudhu) is a vital ritual in Islam, required before performing the five daily prayers. It symbolizes both physical and spiritual purification and plays a critical role in the validity of worship. Despite its significance, studies show that many children lack proper understanding and execution of the ablution process due to limitations in educational accessibility, ineffective pedagogical approaches, and insufficiently engaging instructional media (Idris et al., 2022; Arinal et al., 2019).

Traditional methods, primarily lecture-based instruction, dominate the current teaching of ablution in early education settings. However, such methods are less effective for children aged 5–9, who typically learn better through interactive and visual experiences (Simanjuntak, 2022). Research also indicates that parents, who are often expected to teach ablution at home, may lack the consistency or correct knowledge to effectively pass on this practice (Barutu et al., 2023). These factors contribute to a gap in ablution education, where children struggle with procedural accuracy and understanding.

In light of these challenges, this research focuses on the development of a Virtual Reality (VR) game-based learning application to teach ablution to young children. By leveraging immersive

technology and motion-capture via Kinect camera, the application aims to enhance children’s learning through engaging, interactive experiences. It includes instructional animations, practical demonstrations, and mini games to reinforce learning through active participation.

The objectives of this project are threefold: (i) to design a storyboard for a game-based learning experience on ablution, (ii) to develop a VR-based educational application targeting children aged 5–9, and (iii) to evaluate the user experience and effectiveness of the application. This project seeks to contribute a meaningful alternative to traditional ablution education by offering an accessible, engaging, and pedagogically sound tool that supports both teachers and parents in guiding children toward mastering ablution practices.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The software development model chosen to be used for this project is the ADDIE model. The term ADDIE stands for analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation, which are the five steps of the development process.

2.1 Analysis

For this initial phase, it starts with crafting a comprehensive proposal to guide the development of the Youth Ablution Education using VR approach. With extensive research on various scholar articles and journals through IEEE, Google Scholar and UiTM Digital Library, problem statements and related literatures have been identified. This exploration not only informed the initial problem statements, but also laid the groundwork for detailed and structured project objectives. As for this analyse phase, a survey was designed to collect firsthand insight from the primary stakeholders which is youth and kindergarten students. The purpose of this survey is to observe the target user experience on ablution and VR technology for more insight of this project requirements. Both software and hardware requirement are crucial for the development.

2.2 Design

In the Design phase, a visual sketch, represented by the storyboard, has been developed. Designing the user interface and incorporating main interactions onto the storyboard provides a clear representation of the project's concept and ideas. Additionally, a flowchart has been designed to ensure a seamless process for the project's logic. The flowchart and one of the scene sketches in storyboard are shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Figure 1. Flowchart for Wudu Wonder

Figure 2. Storyboard sketch for one the scene

2.3 Development

This section is where the creation of the game began. With suitable hardware and software requirements alongside with proper project design, Wudu Wonder undergo development stage compromising several components such as asset development, animation development, Kinect integration and gameplay as shown in the following Figure 3 to Figure 11.

Figure 3. Intricate Detail of Modelling Done by The Developer In 3Ds Max

Figure 4. Realism on Materials Done In 3Ds Max

Figure 5. Realistic Feature on Water Physics From The Pipe

Figure 6. The Developer Utilize the Comprehensive Tools In Brekel Studio

2.4 Implementation

Constructivist Learning Theory emphasizes active knowledge construction through experiences and reflections, which is effectively supported by VR environments. M. Alizadeh's summary of the implications of constructivism for instructional design considering VR integration provides valuable insights. In the Wudu Wonder project, this learning theory is implemented as shown in the Table 1 below.

Table 1. Constructivist Learning Theory Approach in Wudu Wonder

Key Aspect	Explanation
<p data-bbox="204 629 628 656">Multiple Representations of Reality</p>	<p data-bbox="809 629 1386 763">Users engage in a virtual environment that offers various perspectives of the mosque and ablution practices, helping them understand the procedures from different angles.</p>
<p data-bbox="204 909 628 936">Natural Complexity of Real World</p>	<p data-bbox="809 909 1318 1043">The VR experience simulates the intricate details of a mosque setting, including the architectural design and the flow of water, providing a realistic learning context.</p>
<p data-bbox="204 1328 400 1355">Authentic Tasks</p>	<p data-bbox="809 1328 1386 1462">Users perform real-life ablution tasks, such as washing specific body parts, in the virtual environment, ensuring they apply 82 theoretical knowledge practically.</p>
<p data-bbox="204 1704 635 1731">Case-Based Learning Environments</p>	<p data-bbox="809 1704 1355 1877">Instead of following a rigid instructional sequence, users navigate through different scenarios that present various challenges and tasks related to ablution, promoting problem-solving and critical thinking.</p>

<p>Reflective Practice</p>	<p>The application provides immediate feedback on the user's actions, allowing them to reflect on their performance and improve their technique through practice in Minigames phase</p>
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2.5 Evaluation

To assess whether this educational VR project thrives the objectives and goals of the project, obtaining user feedback is essential. Evaluation plays a key role in this process and for this case is to tackle user experience on the virtual reality application that teaches children about ablution. All the participants who took part in this testing phase had been measured in aspect of user experience using the widely recognized tool, User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ). The evaluation utilizes Google Form survey as the medium consisting of two sections. First one is Demographic Information, and the second one is the UEQ. A total of 36 respondents actively took part in this project evaluation. Based on the questionnaire obtained data, most of the questionnaire respondents for this project are male, totalling up to 20 students (73.8%). Whereas the rest are females with 16 students (44.4%). The age of all respondents are nine years old.

3. FINDINGS

The evaluation form shown in Table 2 is adapted from the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ). The UEQ consists of 26 items in total; however, only 14 items were selected for the evaluation due to their suitability for children. The remaining items were deemed inappropriate for this age group and thus excluded to ensure that the children could provide meaningful and accurate responses. This careful selection ensures that the evaluation targets aspects most relevant and comprehensible to young users, thereby providing accurate and meaningful feedback on their experience. The excluded items were considered less relevant or potentially confusing for the target age group, which helps maintain the effectiveness and clarity of the evaluation process. The results of the evaluation survey for the "Wudu Wonder" application illustrate how participants perceived their experience with the VR content in terms of attractiveness, perspicuity, efficiency, stimulation, and novelty. Each question required respondents to rate their experience on a scale from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree), ensuring a thorough assessment of the application's user experience. SD, D, N, A and SA stands for Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, Strongly Agree respectively.

Table 2. User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ)

Questions	Factor	Questions (UEQ)	SD (1)	D (2)	N (3)	A (4)	SA (5)
E1	Attractiveness	The game is enjoyable	0	2	1	15	18
E2		The game is attractive	1	0	3	22	10
E3		The game is user friendly	0	1	2	18	15
E4		This game is pleasing	0	2	1	20	13
E5	Perspicuity	This game is understandable	0	1	1	18	16

E6		This game is clear	18	16	0	2	0
E7		This game is easy	0	1	2	16	17
E8	Efficiency	This game is smooth	0	2	3	18	13
E9		This game is efficient	0	1	2	25	8
E10		This game is organized	0	1	3	21	11
E11		This game is useful	0	1	1	11	23
E12	Stimulation	This game is motivating	0	1	0	14	21
E13	Novelty	This game is creative	0	1	0	11	24
E14		The concept of the game is advanced	0	1	1	12	22

4. DISCUSSION

The overall findings from the user experience survey reveal a highly favorable response across several key factors. Attractiveness scored a mean of 4.25, indicating that users find the game enjoyable, appealing, and pleasing. The game's design and enjoyment levels are well-regarded. Perspicuity, with a mean of 3.64, suggests that while the game is generally understandable and user-friendly, there are some areas where clarity could be enhanced. Efficiency also scored 4.25, reflecting that the game is seen as effective and well-functioning, meeting user expectations for performance. The Stimulation factor received a strong mean score of 4.56, showing that the game is highly engaging and motivating for players. Finally, Novelty achieved the highest score of 4.61, indicating that users perceive the game as exceptionally original and creative. The overall total mean of 4.26, with a percentage of 85.2%, highlights a robust positive reception, demonstrating that the game delivers a satisfying and well-rounded user experience as shown in Table 3. While the game excels in creativity and engagement, there is room for improvement in enhancing clarity and comprehensibility.

Table 3. Overall Total Mean Value in Percentage

User Experience	Total Mean
Attractiveness	4.25
Perspicuity	3.64
Efficiency	4.25
Stimulation	4.56
Novelty	4.61
Total Mean	4.26
Overall Total Mean (%)	85.2

5. CONCLUSION

Wudu Wonder stands as a significant educational tool that provides an engaging and immersive learning experience about ablution procedures. The game successfully combines advanced VR technology with educational content, allowing children to learn in an interactive and enjoyable way. The comprehensive development process, from 3D modelling to Kinect integration, and the positive user feedback underscore the project's success in achieving its educational goals. Future enhancements will consider user suggestions to further improve the experience and effectiveness of the game.

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References

- Aldiansyah Barutu, A., Harfiani, R., Muhammadiyah Sumatera Utara, U., Kapten Muchtar Basri No, J., Darat, G. I., Medan Tim, K., Medan, K., & Utara, S. (2023). Pelaksanaan Pembelajaran Wudhu dengan Media Gambar bagi Anak Usia Dini Tadika Al Fikh Orcard Pendamar Indah 2 Selangor. *Journal on Education*, 05(03), 8739–8749.
- Arinal Azalia, Tulenan Virginia, & Jacobus Agustinus. (2019). Pengembangan Aplikasi Tata Cara Wudhu Menggunakan Metode Markerless Augmented Reality. *Jurnal Teknik Informatika*, 14(2).

- Alizadeh, M. (2019). Virtual Reality in the Language Classroom: Theory and Practice. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335969992>
- Idris, T., Wita, A., Rahmi, E., & Warmansyah, J. (2022). Ablution Skills in Early Childhood: The Effect of Big Book Media. *Jurnal Obsesi: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, 6(6), 5549–5557. <https://doi.org/10.31004/obsesi.v6i6.3185>
- Simanjuntak, R. (2022). The Effectiveness Of The Use Of Demonstration Methods For Pai Subjects For Wudhu Materials For Class Ii Students At Sdn 152980 Hajoran I Academic Year 2021-2022. In *Journal of Engineering, Social and Health* (Vol. 1, Issue 2). <https://jesh.globalpublikasiana.com/index.php/gp/>